

The Orbwars is a fun game created to dilute your daily routine with adorable characters, who will face some comic situations and perform funny frights as they go through the game adventure. You will love the characters' ridiculously funny outfits and weapon selection. The Orbwars is an NFT play-to-earn and free-to-play game built on the Terno blockchain.

It's a browser-based game and we focus on the first-mobile design to make the game accessible to everyone.

What is the main game strategy?

- Create the most powerful Tiimon
- Build up the largest territory
- Protect your land
- Breed new characters

The game combines a daily earning option as well as winning token rewards in fights with passive income. The game is free to play. Every new payer will get 1 character - Tiimon. 1 extra Tiimon will be released with every Booster purchase along with 5 items that serve as armor and weapons. Now that you know more about The Orbwars, let's talk about what NFTs are. Non-fungible tokens (NFT) are cryptographic assets that are based on blockchain technology. NFTs can be created in many ways and are a great way to create unique digital assets that can be monetized. They can be virtual, or they can represent physical assets, such as real estate. They are a [Blockchain game](#) key element of the emerging cryptocurrency ecosystem, and they are also an important part of the metaverse, where people live in digital worlds and interact with one another.

The smart contract identifies the token, manages its transferability and sets up the NFT's unique properties. The NFT is a piece of code that is used to represent ownership in a unique asset, such as a digital artwork or a physical property. This code identifies the token, which can be stored in a blockchain ledger, enabling it to have a permanent record of its transactions and to be transferred to a new owner.

NFT tokens can be minted by the creator of an NFT and are then issued on the blockchain, just like a coin or other fungible token. They can be minted in multiple copies, and the number of copies depends on the intended scarcity, or how rare the NFT is intended to be. The value of an NFT depends on the level of uniqueness it has, and it can increase or decrease in price based on a variety of factors. If the NFT is popular, its market value will increase and it could even sell for more than its cost.

NFT communities are growing, and some of them offer special advantages to members, such as shared Discord servers or private Telegram channels. The communities allow you to share ideas with other NFT owners, and sometimes you can even purchase NFTs from other members.

NFTs are a powerful tool for creators, but they can also be a risky business. The NFT creator must be very careful to ensure that the creation of the NFT is as legal and transparent as possible, as ownership can be difficult to verify. Now that you know more about NFTs, it is time to go to the website of The Orbwars:

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Website: www.theorbwars.com

Twitter: https://twitter.com/the_orbwars?s=21&t=_ZmgoY_nrg8aSQsSrrJRdg

Discord: <https://discord.gg/fHkrVjr7eP>

Light paper: <https://redribbonltd.gitbook.io/theorbwars>

Become a liquidity provider and be rewarded: <https://hackmd.io/ab9jM7p8SAavL-oUOHSa9A>